

DP3T Application Case Description, DFD Model, Attacker Model, and Assumptions

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This document describes the DP3T application case, the Data Flow Diagram, attacker model, and security assumptions. The descriptions in this document originate from the documentation site.¹

¹ <https://github.com/DP-3T/documents>

Overview

This document describes a system for secure and privacy-preserving proximity tracing at large scale. The particular description is aimed at enabling a comprehensive threat analysis.

This system provides a technological foundation to help slow the spread of SARS-CoV-2 (but can be broadened to any virus that spreads via proximity) by simplifying and accelerating the process of notifying people who might have been exposed to the virus so that they can take appropriate measures to break its transmission chain. The system is designed with the specific objective to minimise privacy and security risks for individuals and communities and to attain a high level of data protection.

The goal of the proximity tracing system is to determine who has been in close physical proximity to a COVID-19 positive person and thus exposed to the virus, without revealing the contact's identity or where the contact occurred. To achieve this goal, users run a smartphone app that continually broadcasts an ephemeral, pseudo-random ID representing the user's phone and also records the pseudo-random IDs observed from smartphones in close proximity. When a patient is diagnosed with COVID-19, she can upload pseudo-random IDs previously broadcast from her phone to a central server. Prior to the upload, all data remains exclusively on the user's phone and under the user's full control. Other users' apps can use data from the server to locally estimate whether the device's owner was exposed to the virus through close-range physical proximity to a COVID-19 positive person who has uploaded their data. In case the app detects a high risk, it will inform the user.

The system provides the following security and privacy protections:²

- **Ensures data minimization.** The central server only observes anonymous and ephemeral identifiers of COVID-19 positive users without any proximity information. Health authorities learn no information except for the information provided when a user reaches out to them after being notified about a positive test result.

² Troncoso et al., *Decentralized Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing*. DP3t White Paper, 2020

- **Prevents abuse of data.** As the central server receives the minimum amount of information tailored to its requirements, it can neither misuse the collected data for other purposes, nor can it be coerced or subpoenaed to make other data available.
- **Prevents tracking of users.** No entity can track users that have not reported a positive diagnosis. Depending on the specifics of the implementation chosen, others can only track COVID-19 positive users in a small geographical region limited by their capability to deploy infrastructure that can receive broadcasted Bluetooth beacons.
- **Limited data retention and graceful dismantling.** The system will dismantle itself after the end of the epidemic. COVID-19 positive users will stop uploading their data to the central server, and people will stop using the app. Data on the server and in the apps is removed after 14 days by default.

Data Flow Diagram

We briefly describe the main elements of the DFD, the data flows are described together with the functionality below.

EE1. User The end-user using the the contact tracing application on their smartphone.

EE2. Bluetooth device An external bluetooth device with which contact tracing identifiers are exchanged. These can be be other compatible smartphone applications.

EE3. Health Org The health organization that determines for which patients there is a positive COVID case.

P1. Smartphone App The local smartphone applications.

P2. Backend server The backend server responsible for distributing information on positive cases for the decentralized contact tracing.

DS1. Local Storage Local storage on the smartphone applications to retain relevant information for the decentralized contact tracing.

The system functionality is described in four main scenarios:

(1) initialization, (2) local contact tracing, (3) registering infections, and (4) decentralized contact tracing.

1. Bootstrap/initialization

- (DF1) The user provides permission for broadcasting EBIDS and storing received EBIDS locally.

Figure 1: Data Flow Diagram of the DP3T Application

- (DF2) A day key, SK_t for day t , is generated and locally stored, as well as the EBIDs for the day that are generated from that day key.

2. Local contact tracing

- (DF3) Retrieve own EBIDs from storage for broadcasting them during the day.
- (DF4) Retrieve the day key (SK_t) to derive the next day's key (SK_{t+1}).
- (DF5) Store the next day's key (SK_{t+1}) and EBIDs.

- (DF6) Broadcast EBIDS to other bluetooth devices.
- (DF7) Receive EBIDS from other bluetooth devices.
- (DF8) Store the triples of (received EBID, btdata (e.g., signal strength), day) in local storage.

3. *Registering infections*

when a user is suspects a positive infection, a Transaction Authentication Number (TAN) is used to enable the user to upload their case in case of a positive test result.

- (DF9) The user requests the app to generate an Authorization Code AC.
- (DF10) The AC is stored locally to be enable the submission in case of a positive case.
- (DF11) The AC is provided to the user. The user subsequently provides this information to the physician.
- (DF12) For the positive test results, the health organization activates the relevant ACS.
- (DF13) Each positive AC is stored in the backend database.
- (DF14) The user with a positive result gives permission to the app to upload their day keys from when they were contagious.
- (DF15) The AC is retrieved from local storage.
- (DF16) The relevant day key are retrieved from local storage and submitted together with the AC to the backend server.
- (DF17) The backend server checks that the AC is valid.
- (DF18) If the AC is valid, the contract tracing data is stored in the backend database.

4. *Decentralized contact tracing*

- (DF19) The backend server retrieves a list of day keys of positive cases together with the date to make available to the smartphone apps.
- (DF20) The smartphone app downloads the contact tracing data.
- (DF21) The smartphone app retrieves the local list of contact tracing data and checks whether any of the received EBIDS come from the positive day case.

- The the number of EBIDs from positive cases is above a certain risk threshold, the user receives a notification to get tested.

Attacker Model

In this section, we provide a preliminary analysis of the types of adversaries that we take into account when carrying out the security and privacy analysis. For each of these adversaries, we describe their incentives and technical capabilities.

Regular user. A typical user of the system that is assumed to be able to install and use the application by navigating its user interface (UI). They exclusively look at information available via the app's UI to infer private information about other users.

Tech-savvy user (Blackhat/Whitehat hacker, NGOs, Academic researchers, etc.). This user has access to the system via the mobile App. In addition, she can set up (BT, WiFi, and Mobile) antennas to eavesdrop locally. Finally, she can decompile/modify the app, and she has access to the backend source code.

- (Whitehat hacker) Will investigate the App code, the information in the phone, and will look at what information is exchanged with the server (using an antenna or software installed on the phone, e.g., Lumen) or broadcast via Bluetooth (passive).
- (Malicious) Can DOS the system (targeted or system-wide), deviate from protocols, and actively broadcast Bluetooth identifiers.

Eavesdropper (Internet Service Provider, Local System administrators, Bluetooth sniffer). They can observe network communication (i.e., source and destination of packages, payload, time) and/or BLE broadcast messages.

- (Network adversary) Can use observed network traffic to attempt to determine the state of a user (e.g., whether they are at-risk, COVID-19 positive, etc.).
- (Local Bluetooth BLE Sniffer) Can observe local Bluetooth broadcasts (possibly with a powerful antenna to cover a wider area) and try to trace people.

It should be noted however that in many instances, for individuals or companies to use data in this way, or to collect data about passers-by to try and estimate their infection status based on the announced identifiers, will fall foul of a range of existing national

and European laws around data protection, ePrivacy and computer misuse.

Health authority. Receives information about COVID-19 positive users as part of their normal operations to diagnose patients. By design, the health authority learns information about at-risk people only when these at-risk people themselves reach out to the health authority (e.g., after receiving a notification from their app).

Backend and App developers. Can access all data stored at the servers. Moreover, the backend can query data from the mobile app in the same way that it would do during normal operations (in our designs, it can only change the data downloaded by the smartphones). They could also change the code of their backend software and the code of the mobile apps (including parameters related to proximity tracing). We assume they will not modify the mobile app because such action would be detectable. They can combine and correlate information, request information from apps, combine with other public information to learn (co-)location information of individuals.

State-level adversary (Law enforcement, intelligence agencies, etc). This adversary has the combined capabilities of the tech-savvy user and the eavesdropper. In addition, a state-level adversary can obtain subpoenas that give them the capabilities of the health authority, or the backend. Their goal is to obtain information about the population or to target particular individuals. They may be interested in past information, already stored in the system, or future information that will enable them to trace target individuals based on observed EBIDs.

Unlimited-budget adversary. An adversary with an unlimited budget, e.g., large organizations and (foreign) nation states, has the capabilities of tech-savvy users but can deploy these at a much larger scale. Additionally, such an adversary might be able to gain full control over the project's infrastructure such as the backend. The goals of this adversary might be to learn information about the population or individuals (cf. a state-level adversary) or to disrupt the proximity tracing system, resulting in a form of denial of service. One form of disruption is to try cause a sizable part of the population to receive fake at-risk notifications by deploying antennas in public locations (e.g., airports, train stations, shopping malls, or parliament buildings) and relaying messages far and wide. This relay attack increases the chances of "at risk" contacts for the targeted population because their phones will perceive proximity where there is none.